

Probiotics and mental disorders

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Abstract

Neurodegenerative and neuropsychiatric disorders continue to pose significant public health challenges due to their progressive course, high prevalence, and substantial socioeconomic impact. Conventional therapies are often limited by pharmacoresistance, side effects, and suboptimal efficacy, emphasizing the need for complementary and integrative approaches. Emerging research underscores the pivotal role of the gut–brain axis (GBA) in neurological health, highlighting psychobiotics and specific probiotic strains with potential mental health benefits as promising adjunctive interventions. This review synthesizes current evidence on the GBA's involvement in conditions such as Alzheimer's disease, Parkinson's disease, depression, and anxiety. We explore how psychobiotics may influence neuroinflammation, oxidative stress, and neurotransmitter signaling, thereby supporting cognitive function and emotional regulation. Findings from both preclinical and clinical studies are examined, including quality-of-life measures and neuropsychiatric comorbidities. Additionally, we discuss recent innovations, including precision psychobiotics, microbiota–drug interactions, and their implications for overlapping metabolic and neurodegenerative disorders.

Keywords

Gut–brain axis, mental health, microbiota dysbiosis, neurodegenerative diseases, neuropsychiatric disorders, probiotics

Introduction

From the first description of *Lactobacillus bulgaricus* by Stamen Grigorov to today's understanding of probiotics, the thread of knowledge continues to unravel. In modern global society, where people are subjected to daily stress, widespread antibiotic use, poor nutrition, and a variety of harmful external factors, the balance of the gastrointestinal flora is constantly disrupted. Hippocrates' brilliant insight that “all diseases begin in the gut” finds contemporary confirmation. It is no coincidence that in Europe, probiotics and probiotic foods are among the most stable segments of the food market. The gut microbiota is increasingly viewed as a symbiotic partner in maintaining good health. Metagenomic approaches could help to understand how the complex gut

microbial ecosystem participates in controlling brain development and function. This may be significant for future therapeutic developments, such as probiotics, prebiotics, and nutritional approaches for mental disorders.

Aim of the review

The aim of this review is to synthesize current data on the relationship between microbiota dysbiosis (imbalance in the microbiota composition) and the onset or progression of major mental disorders and to explore potential therapeutic opportunities targeting microbiota dysbiosis in psychiatric patients.

Mental disorders and global challenges

Neurological disorders, including depression, anxiety, Alzheimer's disease (AD), and Parkinson's disease (PD), represent an increasing global public health concern (Obreshkova et al. 2016; Georgiev et al. 2025). Beyond their profound impact on the quality of life of millions of individuals, these conditions also place a substantial economic and societal burden (Toader et al. 2023). Projections predict a significant increase in the prevalence of mental disorders worldwide. Their rising prevalence is closely linked to population aging, which represents the primary risk factor for most neurodegenerative disorders and a key contributor to the development and progression of psychiatric conditions (Han et al. 2025).

However, the percentage of patients successfully treated with classical psychiatric therapies remains unsatisfactory. Resistance to psychotropic drugs can be attributed to various clinical, pharmacological, pharmacokinetic, and pharmacodynamic factors. This situation highlights the urgent need for innovative and complementary therapeutic strategies that extend beyond traditional pharmacological treatments (Hadzhieva et al. 2023; Mitra et al. 2024).

The role of the microbiota in mental disorders

Findings in animal studies suggest that the microbiota may have an underestimated influence on host behavior and drug metabolism, which could explain the ineffectiveness or increased side effects of psychotropic medications. The microbiota represents a community of microorganisms living in a specific environment. As mentioned, the human gut microbiota contains over 1014 bacteria, primarily anaerobic, as well as yeasts, fungi, and viruses (Turrioni et al. 2008).

This means there are 10 times more prokaryotic cells than eukaryotic cells in the human body. Even more impressive are the genetic data: the gut microbiome contains over 150 times more unique genes than the human genome (Qin et al. 2010).

The need for complementary approaches in neuroprotection

Neuroinflammation and oxidative stress are central mechanisms in the pathophysiology of neurodegenerative and neuropsychiatric disorders, contributing to neuronal loss, impaired neurotransmission, and cognitive or behavioral decline. These processes are driven by excessive glial cell activation, cytokine release (e.g., TNF- α , IL-1 β , and IL-6), blood-brain barrier (BBB) dysfunction, and infiltration of peripheral immune cells into brain tissue.

Despite advances in pharmacological therapies, high treatment costs, resistance, limited accessibility, and potential side effects highlight the need for innovative and integrative approaches to neuroprotection.

Natural compounds with antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties, as well as interventions targeting the gut-brain axis (GBA), are attracting increasing attention as promising complementary strategies (Van Schependom and D'Haeseleer 2023). Among these, natural compounds with antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activity show encouraging neuroprotective effects (Singh 2023). The gut-brain axis is increasingly recognized as a key modulator of brain health, with growing evidence linking gut dysbiosis to neuroinflammation and cognitive decline. Psychobiotics—a subgroup of probiotics targeting the gut-brain axis—represent a promising avenue. These microorganisms not only reduce neuroinflammation but also influence neurotransmitter synthesis (e.g., 5-HT and GABA), regulate hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis activity, and support synaptic plasticity (Luo et al. 2022; Stolzer et al. 2023).

The dual action of psychobiotics, simultaneously targeting neurodegenerative and neuropsychiatric components, makes them a valuable adjunct to existing therapies. Consequently, their inclusion in integrated therapeutic paradigms may enhance neuroprotection, improve quality of life, and reduce the economic burden of these disorders.

Microbiota dysbiosis and potential consequences on central nervous system function

Several recent reviews summarize key data on the influence of the microbiota on the central nervous system, primarily based on *in vitro* studies and research involving animals and humans with inflammatory bowel disorders (Kennedy et al. 2012; McFarland et al. 2018).

The potential role of the microbiota in the onset or progression of mental disorders and new therapeutic possibilities targeting microbiota dysbiosis in psychiatric conditions are also being explored.

The term “dysbiosis” refers to situations in which the microbial composition and functions are shifted from their normal, beneficial state to another that is harmful to the host's health. Microbiota dysbiosis can negatively affect the functioning of the central nervous system (CNS) through various intertwined pathways, collectively forming the brain-gut axis. These pathways can be described as follows:

- Modification of intestinal permeability, allowing endotoxins to enter the systemic bloodstream. Lipopolysaccharides (LPS), a potent pro-inflammatory endotoxin in the cell walls of Gram-negative bacteria, can alter neuronal activity in the limbic system (e.g., increased amygdala activity) and activate microglia, thereby potentially contributing to chronic inflammation in the central nervous system of the host (Qin et al. 2007). The leakage of LPS from the

gut can trigger peripheral inflammatory responses that lead to *de novo* production of cytokines in the brain. Improving the epithelial barrier can reduce the passage of bacteria and their waste products, thereby potentially halting the inflammatory response.

- Synthesis of neuropeptides (Kastin et al. 2010). Modulation of local and peripheral inflammation. The gut microbiota regulates the development of lymphoid structures and modulates the differentiation of immune cell subgroups, thereby maintaining homeostatic interactions between the host and the gut microbiota (Sommer et al. 2013).
- Certain specific bacteria, including members of the Enterobacteriaceae family, seem to be better adapted for survival in inflamed gut conditions compared to anaerobic commensals that dominate in healthy individuals. Considering the established anti-inflammatory effects of butyrate (a short-chain fatty acid), the depletion of butyrate-producing bacteria in dysbiosis could lead to inflammation and depression (Alatan et al. 2024). Supplementation with *Lactobacillus helveticus* NS8 alleviated behavioral, neural, endocrine, and microbiota abnormalities in an endogenous rat model of depression. Bipolar disorder (Goldstein et al. 2009) and schizophrenia (Nemani et al. 2015) are associated with dysregulation of immune responses, as reflected by abnormal profiles of circulating pro- and anti-inflammatory cytokines in affected individuals.
- Reduced absorption of beneficial and essential nutrients (e.g., vitamins, polyunsaturated fatty acids), increased synthesis of harmful compounds (e.g., ammonia, phenols, indoles, sulfides, and amines), decreased antioxidant status, and increased lipid peroxidation, leading to malabsorption of carbohydrates.
- Activation or deactivation of the autonomic nervous system, which is directly connected to the nucleus tractus solitarius. This nucleus, in turn, sends direct noradrenergic ascending signals to areas in the brain related to the regulation of anxiety states (namely, the amygdala, the cholinergic system, and the cortex) (Bercik et al. 2012).
- Modulation of neurotrophic factors produced by the brain.
- Increased bacterial overgrowth in the small intestine or stomach and gut pathogens (e.g., *Helicobacter pylori*).

The role of the gut microbiota in psychiatric disorders. "Mechanisms of communication between the gut and the brain (GBA)"

The gut microbiota, with all its complex interactions with various systems in the body, is increasingly recognized as a key factor in the development and maintenance of psychiatric disorders. Although research in humans is still at an early stage, animal models demonstrate that the mi-

crobiota plays a fundamental role in the genesis of several physiological systems, including the hypothalamic–pituitary–adrenal (HPA) axis, the serotonergic system, and immune-inflammatory processes. The microbiota can influence the central nervous system (CNS) through multiple pathways; however, definitive conclusions in humans are still lacking, particularly with regard to psychiatric conditions such as autism, depression, and anxiety.

The gut–brain axis (GBA) primarily consists of three major components:

1. Gut microbiota: The gut microbiota is a complex ecosystem comprising bacteria, viruses, and fungi, with bacterial populations being the most extensively studied. Advances in microbiome research have revealed how microbial genes influence host metabolism and immune signaling. The microbiota plays a critical role in maintaining intestinal mucosal integrity and regulating immune responses by interacting with the host at the molecular level (Ursell et al. 2012).
2. Gastrointestinal tract: The gastrointestinal tract (GIT) represents the second component of the GBA, in which enterocytes (intestinal epithelial cells) and the mucus barrier function as a selective barrier and an interactive interface. These structures allow beneficial microbes to thrive and actively participate in the host's immune and metabolic functions. The intestinal mucosa not only protects the host from pathogens but also plays a key role in nutrient absorption and the regulation of immune responses (Aburto et al. 2024).
3. Enteric nervous system (ENS): The enteric nervous system, the third component of the GBA, comprises neurons, interneurons, motor neurons, and glial cells organized into the myenteric and submucosal plexuses. The ENS is capable of autonomous function but also communicates with the central nervous system (CNS). This system is often referred to as the "second brain" because it can coordinate functions such as digestion and the secretion of digestive enzymes without direct input (Fung et al. 2020).

These three components—microbiota, gastrointestinal tract, and enteric nervous system—form the foundation of gut–brain communication, which influences a wide range of physiological processes and may be crucial for both mental and physical health. When this communication pathway is disrupted, various diseases may develop, including neurodegenerative and psychiatric disorders.

Diseases associated with microbiota dysbiosis in humans

Microbiota dysbiosis has been linked to various neurological and psychiatric disorders, including depression, anxiety, bipolar disorder, schizophrenia, and even neurodegenerative diseases such as Parkinson's disease and

Alzheimer's disease. The imbalance in the gut microbiota composition may contribute to the onset or progression of these disorders by triggering systemic inflammation, disrupting neurotransmitter pathways, and influencing the immune response. Chronic inflammatory bowel disorders are strongly associated with microbiota dysbiosis and show a high comorbidity with psychiatric disorders.

Irritable bowel syndrome (IBS) overview

IBS is associated with cognitive disturbances, particularly in recalling emotional memories and performing on verbal IQ tests. It is considered a paradigmatic disorder of the gut–brain axis due to its prevalence (~10% in Western populations), high comorbidity with psychiatric disorders (especially mood and anxiety disorders), and statistical associations with childhood abuse.

Acute bacterial gastroenteritis and the use of certain antibiotics that alter the gut microbiota are recognized risk factors. The male-to-female ratio is roughly 2.5, with women more often presenting diarrhea-predominant IBS (IBS-D) and men constipation-predominant IBS (IBS-C).

Microbiota dysbiosis in IBS is characterized by reduced bacterial diversity, decreased Firmicutes, and increased intestinal barrier permeability. Specifically, IBS-D patients tend to have fewer *Lactobacillus* species, whereas IBS-C patients show higher levels of *Veillonella* species.

Autism spectrum disorder (ASD)

Microbiota dysbiosis has been extensively studied in autism, or autism spectrum disorder (ASD), a generalized developmental disorder characterized by impaired social interactions, communication difficulties, and restrictive or repetitive behaviors, often accompanied by gastrointestinal issues (Alharthi et al. 2022).

Several research teams have examined the gut microbiota of the autistic population and found differences in microbial composition compared to healthy controls (Kushak et al. 2011). Specifically:

- Children with autism exhibit a tenfold increase in *Clostridium* and elevated levels of Bacteroidetes and *Desulfovibrio*, as well as a reduced number of Firmicutes and *Bifidobacterium* species compared to healthy children (Chidambaram et al. 2020).
- Alterations in intestinal permeability have also been observed in autism. Increased gut permeability has been detected not only in individuals with autism but also in their first-degree relatives, suggesting that these changes may be related to disease pathogenesis rather than being a consequence of autistic behavior.
- A study reports elevated levels of lipopolysaccharides (LPS) in the blood of individuals with ASD, accompanied by increased peripheral levels of IL-6, a neu-

rotransmitter-related cytokine. Lipopolysaccharides (LPS) are endotoxins found in Gram-negative bacteria (e.g., *Desulfovibrio* and *Bacteroides*) that can disrupt the blood–brain barrier and interfere with neuropsychiatric communication (Mezzelani et al. 2015).

- Compared with typically developing children presenting gastrointestinal symptoms, some children with ASD show immune cell infiltration (e.g., lymphocytes, monocytes, NK cells, and eosinophils) within the walls of the gastrointestinal tract. The gut contains a microbial ecosystem composed of various bacteria, viruses, and fungi that develop and mature during early childhood. Alterations in gut microbiota composition may influence cognitive and behavioral outcomes (e.g., depression, anxiety, increased stress levels); however, these symptoms may be reversible through the restoration of beneficial microorganisms in the gut via probiotic supplementation (Liu et al. 2015; Hoban et al. 2017; Berding et al. 2018).

Recently, it has been demonstrated that gut microbes can regulate microRNA expression in the amygdala and prefrontal cortex, providing at least one mechanism through which the microbiota may influence cognitive processes, emotions, and behavior.

Anxiety and depression

Currently, there is no definitive evidence linking anxiety disorders and depression directly with the gut microbiota. However, experimental studies suggest that the microbiota may play an important role in the regulation of stress, anxiety, and mood throughout life. It has been shown that the administration of endotoxin LPS in healthy individuals may be linked to an increased frequency of anxiety and depression, which are in turn associated with elevated salivary cortisol, plasma norepinephrine, and pro-inflammatory cytokines (Heidarzadeh-Rad et al. 2020; Walden et al. 2023; Zhu 2023).

Stress

Stress plays a significant role in the development of symptoms that contribute to various diseases. It can induce a range of disorders, including gastrointestinal, physical, and psychological symptoms (Diop et al. 2008). Probiotics are known to help regulate or modulate gastrointestinal functions. The aim of this clinical study was to investigate the effects of a probiotic preparation on stress-induced symptoms in volunteers. A study was conducted with participants exhibiting stress-related symptoms. Maritime professions place crews under significant psychological stress, particularly during long voyages in extreme environments. One potential approach to supporting mental well-being is the use of psychobiotics. This study investigates the effect of a probiotic formula containing *Lactobacillus bulgaricus* DWT1 (with *Streptococcus thermophilus* DWT4) on the

mental health of the crew aboard RV421 “St. St. Cyril and Methodius” during voyages supporting the 31st and 32nd Bulgarian Antarctic Expeditions (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. “St. St. Cyril and Methodius”, supporting the 31st and 32nd Bulgarian Antarctic Expeditions.

Crew members are exposed for approximately 140 days per year to extreme physical and psychosocial stressors, including climate changes, time zone shifts, isolation, confined living and working conditions, and prolonged separation from family. The study involved 46 male sailors (mean age 36), divided voluntarily into two groups: Group A (20 participants) receiving a daily probiotic dose and Group B (26 participants) not receiving probiotics.

Psychological assessments were conducted before departure and after return. Results showed no statistically significant increase in anxiety and depression levels in the probiotic group after the voyage, whereas the non-probiotic group demonstrated a significant increase in both anxiety and depression. Sleep analysis revealed a correlation between pre-voyage sleep quality and post-voyage sleep changes, highlighting the interaction between sleep, accumulated fatigue, stress, and mental processing.

Overall, the findings suggest that probiotic supplementation may help protect against increases in anxiety and depression in seafarers exposed to prolonged extreme conditions, supporting its potential role as a preventive psychobiotic intervention in maritime and expedition settings (Georgieva 2022; Stoeva et al. 2023).

Potential therapeutic approaches for addressing dysbiosis in mental health

In light of the emerging role of microbiota dysbiosis in mental health, probiotics, prebiotics, and dietary interventions may serve as novel adjunctive treatments for these disorders. There is growing evidence that psychobiotics—a specific probiotic strain capable of modulating the gut–brain axis—may play a crucial role in the management of psychiatric disorders by restoring mi-

crobial balance, reducing inflammation, and improving neurotransmitter signaling.

Probiotic treatment and therapeutic applications in psychiatry

The idea of treating psychiatric disorders with probiotics is not new. In 1910, Dr. George Porter Philips reported that a gelatin-serum formula with live lactic acid bacteria improved depressive symptoms in adult patients with melancholia (Philips 1910). Current evidence for the effectiveness of probiotics in various diseases (mainly gastrointestinal disorders) is controversial, further complicated by the fact that treatment protocols in different studies are highly heterogeneous, with varying strains, doses, treatment durations, and methods of administration.

Probiotics are also found in foods: about 35% of all lactic acid bacteria isolated from raw fruits and vegetables can survive stomach conditions.

Probiotics can stabilize the mucosal barrier by increasing mucin expression, reducing bacterial overgrowth, stimulating mucosal immunity (secretory IgA), and synthesizing antioxidants. The main probiotics used in current commercial products are lactic acid bacteria, including *Lactobacillus* (e.g., *Lactobacillus casei*, *Lactobacillus reuteri*, *Lactobacillus fermentum*, *Lactobacillus plantarum*, *Lactobacillus paracasei*, *Lactobacillus salivarius*, and *Lactobacillus rhamnosus*) and *Bifidobacterium* (e.g., *Bifidobacterium bifidum*, *Bifidobacterium infantis*, and *Bifidobacterium longum*) (Ng et al. 2018). The application of a single strain of *Bifidobacterium* or *Lactobacillus* can increase the quantity of both species in the gastrointestinal tract (GIT) in humans, suggesting that changes in the gut microbiota may be more significant. Rao et al. showed that these changes were significantly associated with improved anxiety symptoms in 39 patients with chronic fatigue syndrome, who were treated daily with *Lactobacillus casei* for 2 months (Rao et al. 2009).

It has been found that oral probiotics are beneficial for reducing SIBO (small intestinal bacterial overgrowth) in the small intestine.

Dietary modifications

Diet plays a critical role in shaping the gut microbiota, with various foods influencing the growth of beneficial bacteria such as *Lactobacillus* and *Bifidobacterium*. Key foods rich in antioxidants—such as cocoa, coffee, green tea, blueberries, and curcumin—have been shown to support the growth of these bacteria, which can positively impact mental health. For example, coffee consumption has been linked to a reduced risk of depression and cognitive decline, while curcumin can prevent intestinal permeability. Green tea, on the other hand, can reduce inflammation and blood–brain barrier permeability during infections (Bereswill et al. 2010).

Additionally, orange juice, likely due to its flavonoid content, helps prevent the rise of endotoxins when consumed alongside high-fat, high-carbohydrate meals. Long-term consumption of honey has similar benefits, improving gut microbiota diversity and mitigating anxiety and cognitive decline.

Magnesium and zinc also play important roles. Deficiencies in these minerals are associated with depression and affect gut microbiota diversity and intestinal permeability. Both are crucial for the activity of intestinal alkaline phosphatase, an enzyme that supports microbiota health and reduces systemic endotoxins (Chepulis et al. 2009).

In summary, dietary modifications—ranging from antioxidant-rich foods to magnesium and zinc intake—can have a significant impact on gut health, which in turn may influence mental health outcomes.

Prebiotics

Prebiotics are indigestible food components that promote the growth or activity of beneficial bacteria in the colon. While not yet studied for major psychiatric disorders, prebiotics could be useful alongside probiotics.

Postbiotics

Postbiotics are functional molecules produced by the microbiota that influence health. This emerging approach involves supplementing the diet with molecules that are depleted in certain diseases, allowing the microbiota to convert them into bioactive forms. For example, indole (from tryptophan) reduces inflammation and pathogen colonization and increases mucin production. Changes in butyrate, acetate, and propionate also correlate with worsened health, highlighting the microbiota's importance in gastrointestinal health (Claesson et al. 2012).

Antibiotics

Antibiotics, such as minocycline and tetracycline, can have profound effects on the gut microbiota and have been used to treat psychiatric disorders such as schizophrenia and depression. Although the microbiota generally recovers after antibiotic treatment, some species-level changes may persist, potentially enhancing therapeutic effects even after treatment ends (Miyaoaka et al. 2012).

Fecal transplantation

Fecal transplantation involves transferring microbiota from a healthy donor to a sick individual to restore gut health. It has shown success in treating *Clostridium difficile* infections but is not widely used due to the risks of introducing new pathogens. Ongoing research aims to optimize the procedure and expand its use.

Activated charcoal

Activated charcoal is used to treat poisonings by binding toxins in the digestive tract, potentially alleviating the harmful effects of microbiota dysbiosis. Some studies suggest it may also help improve psychiatric symptoms by binding toxins secreted into the gut.

Conclusion: the role of gut microbiota in psychiatric disorders

The role of the human gut microbiota in the genesis or maintenance of psychiatric disorders is still in the early stages of research, but it currently represents one of the most promising directions for investigation in psychiatry. While animal models suggest that microbiota function plays a major role in the genesis of the hypothalamic–pituitary–adrenal (HPA) axis, serotonergic system, and immune-inflammatory system, and that the microbiota can affect the central nervous system (CNS) via multiple pathways, few studies have been conducted in humans. Autism is currently the psychiatric disorder where the role of the microbiota is best studied. Some therapeutic possibilities targeting potential microbiota dysbiosis have already been explored, such as probiotic applications or dietary modifications, but with conflicting results. Further research is needed to determine which patients might benefit most from microbiota-based therapies.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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